

PECULIARITIES OF MORAL EDUCATION AT THE EARLY SCHOOL AGE

Lect. Zorica TRIFF, PhD

*Technical University of Cluj, North University Center of Baia Mare, Romania
ztriff@yahoo.com*

ABSTRACT: Peculiarities of Moral Education at the Early School Age.

The fundamental purpose of moral education in school consists in the formation of the individual as a moral subject, who thinks and acts in the spirit of the requirements and demands of social morality, values, norms and rules.

Childhood is the most important period in an individual's life, it is the starting point for his further development. That is why, from an early age, the child must be given the optimal environment for the formation and development of positive character traits, appropriate and formative social-moral behaviors.

Keywords: *freedom, values, rules, moral norms, education, school, family.*

During the period of early schooling, when the child makes contact for the first time in a free way with the environment, but has not yet managed to satisfactorily manage his own needs, the first violations of the norms of moral conduct appear, to which the parents react. The demands on the child increase, due to the fact that his horizon of action widens, he comes into contact with social groups and their rules.

During this period, behavior that conforms to social norms is positively reinforced, through laudatory rewards, approval, affection, and negative behavior is met with punishment, withdrawal of privileges, admonition, or, in the worst case, physical aggression. In this period of age, distortion of the truth frequently occurs in children, and just as frequently this is harshly punished by parents.

The child's thinking is egocentric, in which his own desires and pleasures are sovereign, he cannot understand the fact that others have different feelings and opinions, he cannot correlate his point of view with that of others, he projects his own sensations and perceptions onto others.

Likewise, thinking is dominated by animism, it animates the surrounding objects, it does not differentiate between the fantastic and the possible. In this context, the distortion of the truth is normal, it is part of the development process.

Whether it appears in the form of an invented story, with more or less real characters, or whether it is aimed at obtaining favors, punishment is not a solution when untruth occurs. It is, however, a good opportunity to teach the child to tell the truth, using rewards and encouragement when he does so.

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The reform in education proposes, as a priority, the change of purposes, in order to operate, as a consequence, some substantial transformations at the level of the organizational structure and in the field of the program of instructive-educational activities, followed, in the logic of curriculum design, "by some methodological recommendations" necessary for each teaching staff for the effective implementation and continuous, formative evaluation of the proposed contents.

In the context of the goals of school education, training supports the "basic structure" of the schoolboy's education intellectually, but also morally-affectively, psychophysically, but also aesthetically.

In this direction, the entire activity designed for the medium and long term is engaged in order to form the "self-image", the "identity consciousness".

The fundamental dimensions of education are specific to the training-development activity of the personality.

The general contents of the personality training-development activity are aimed at:

- ✦ moral education that reflects the pedagogical values of moral good;
- ✦ intellectual education that reflects the pedagogical values of scientific truth;
- ✦ technological education that reflects the pedagogical values of applied scientific truth;
- ✦ aesthetic education that reflects the pedagogical values of beauty from art, nature, society;
- ✦ physical education that reflects the pedagogical values of sport, physical health.

The curriculum aims to achieve the following goals of early education:

- ✦ the free, integrated and harmonious development of the child's personality, depending on his own rhythm and his needs, supporting his autonomous and creative formation;
- ✦ developing the ability to interact with other children, adults and the environment in order to acquire new knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviors.

Encouraging explorations, exercises, trials and experiments, as autonomous learning experiences;

- ✦ the discovery of each child's own identity, autonomy and the development of a positive self-image;
- ✦ supporting the child in the acquisition of knowledge, abilities, skills and attitudes necessary for him when entering school and throughout his life.

Since the aims of education in the early period aim at the global development of the child, the framework and reference objectives of the curriculum are formulated by experiential domains, taking into account the milestones established by the developmental domains.

In this sense, the experiential fields become tools for achieving certain objectives and, at the same time, measuring tools for the child's development, in the context in which they indicate skills, capacities, abilities, contents specific to the fields of development.

It is essential to know and respect the rules necessary for integration into social life, as well as personal safety rules (e.g.: the importance of healthy foods for the human body; activity and game rules, in order to avoid dangerous situations; minimum rules protection of nature and the danger of violating them; rules regarding the protection of one's life and those around, etc.);

To adapt his own behavior to the requirements of the group he lives in (family, kindergarten, playgroup);

To negotiate and participate in joint decisions;

To appreciate in concrete situations some behaviors and attitudes in relation to predetermined and known norms;

To live in positive affective states in relationships with those around, to show friendship, tolerance, harmony, simultaneously with learning self-control;

To describe and identify local elements specific to our country and the area in which he lives (relief elements, geographical location, socio-cultural, historical, religious, ethnic objectives);

To know and use simple work tools to carry out a practical activity;

To know different working materials, natural or synthetic;

To perform simple work operations with natural and synthetic materials;

To identify, design and find as many solutions as possible to achieve the proposed theme within the practical activities;

To relate to the immediate environment, contributing to its enrichment through personal works;

To acquire correct hygienic behaviors and attitudes towards one's own person and towards other beings and objects;

To acquire the ability to enter into a relationship with those around, respecting norms of correct behavior and useful to others;

To form practical and household skills;

To behave appropriately in different social contexts. Among the three categories of objectives - cognitive, affective and sensory-motor - the most difficult to define and operationalize are the affective-emotional ones.

In order to highlight the social aspect, essential in schoolchildren's education, the name socio-affective objectives is preferred.

A good definition and operationalization of the objectives can determine the efficiency of the educational act in all its stages: design, organization, implementation and evaluation.

Conclusions

The fundamental purpose of moral education in school consists in the formation of the individual as a moral subject, who thinks and acts in the spirit of the requirements and exigencies of social morality, values¹, norms and rules.

School age, so important for personality development, requires understanding and tact from the teacher. For many children, school represents the opportunity to socialize, to develop their personality and creativity, to integrate more easily, later in life. Among the forms of school activity that contribute to the creation of emotional events are: playing, reading, extracurricular activities.

The main forms through which the tasks of moral education are carried out are: the educational process, games and extracurricular activities. In school, there are different types of activities that can significantly contribute to the moral education of children.

Thus, stages of moral education can be envisioned depending on the components of ethical behavior: the formation of elementary moral habits, the awakening of moral conscience, the cultivation of moral convictions, the stimulation of affective behaviors, the formation of ethical attitudes, as well as the structuring of values and the moral ideal.

In the formation and cultivation of these components, you can act in two ways: encouraging positive attitudes and reducing or preventing negative ones. Education for moral values² is facilitated by the presence of a positive, stimulating affective framework, generated by the teacher's behavior,

1 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, "Plea for Human Dignity", in *Scientia Moralitas. Human Dignity - A Contemporary Perspectives*, The Scientia Moralitas Research Institute, Beltsville, MD, United States of America, 2016, Volume 1, pp. 29-43.

2 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, "Current Values of Education and Culture", in *Proceedings of the 24th International RAIS Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities*, August 15-16, 2021, Princeton, NJ, United States of America, pp. 87-92.

more precisely, respect for children's personality, the establishment of permissive relationships with children, the promotion of a balanced discourse, sincerity and faith in the children's ethical dispositions, being indispensable levers for the formation of conscience and moral conduct.³

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3 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, "Valences of Education", în *Proceedings of the 24th International RAIS Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities*, August 15-16, 2021, Princeton, NJ, United States of America, pp. 190-196.